

1 **Vsig10 and Vstm5, immune receptors with apparent function during TE specification in utero.**

2
3 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
4 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
5 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
6 East Islip, NY USA 11730

7 We measured total transcription in the inner cell mass (ICM) and the trophectoderm (TE) of the human
8 embryo to understand the mechanisms underlying TE commitment. We describe here discovery of Vsig10
9 and Vstm5, immune receptors with apparent function during TE specification in utero.

10 Citations

11 1. Wang, J., Manick, B., Renelt, M., Suin, J., Hansen, L., Person, A., Kalabokis, V. and Wu, G., 2019.
12 VSTM4 is a novel negative regulator of T cell activation. The Journal of Immunology, 202(1_Supplement),
13 pp.124-4.

14 2. Levin, S.D., Taft, D.W., Brandt, C.S., Bucher, C., Howard, E.D., Chadwick, E.M., Johnston, J.,
15 Hammond, A., Bontadelli, K., Ardourel, D. and Hebb, L., 2011. Vstm3 is a member of the CD28 family and
16 an important modulator of T-cell function. European journal of immunology, 41(4), pp.902-915.
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28